

TABLE I

Copper complex of	Solvents	λ_{\max} cm^{-1}	$\langle g_0 \rangle$	$\langle A_0 \rangle$ $\times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	α^2	K
o-Hydroxyacetophenone	Dioxane	15 220	2.06	74	0.090 0	0.263 2
	DMF	15 200	2.09	73	0.156 7	0.290 5
	Pyridine	15 120	2.10	71	0.181 5	0.294 9
	Piperidine	15 038	—	—	—	—
Resacetophenone	Dioxane	15 250	2.07	72	0.110 9	0.271 4
	DMF	15 220	2.09	70	0.158 7	0.282 2
	Pyridine	15 150	2.11	67	0.207 1	0.293 8
	Piperidine	15 038	—	—	—	—
Peonol	Dioxane	15 150	2.07	73	0.110 2	0.270 5
	DMF	15 140	2.10	70	0.181 9	0.292 2
	Pyridine	15 105	2.12	69	0.229 0	0.309 3
	Piperidine	15 020	—	—	—	—
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	Dioxane	15 150	2.07	72	0.110 9	0.271 4
	DMF	15 120	2.09	68	0.160 0	0.272 6
	Pyridine	14 950	2.12	61	0.234 0	0.287 3
	Piperidine	14 920	—	—	—	—

exhibit four hyperfinelines with spin dependent line widths due to the tumbling motion of the microcrystalline units. This tumbling motion in solution will average the anisotropic g and A values observed in the solids. The values of $\langle g \rangle$ for the Cu^{II} complexes of hydroxy aldehydes and ketones are slightly greater in pyridine and dimethylformamide than in dioxane (Table 1). The $\langle g \rangle$ values are in the order, pyridine \rangle dimethylformamide \rangle dioxane, which indicate that the pyridine and dimethylformamide interact to a greater extent than dioxane. This is also evident from the shift of optical absorption peaks to a lower frequency side in the electronic spectra of these complexes.

The $\langle A \rangle$ values of the copper(II) hydroxy ketone and aldehyde complexes showed lower values in pyridine and dimethylformamide than dioxane (Table 1). The variation of the splitting with the solvent thus indicates that the stronger the solvated complex, the smaller is the value of the unpaired electron's wave function at the nucleus. Apparently the bonding solvent pulls the electron away from the copper.

In a spectrum recorded in solution the isotropic nuclear hyperfine splitting $\langle A \rangle$ is related to the covalence of the unpaired electron by the equation,

$$\langle A \rangle = p(-\alpha^2 k_0 + g - 2.0023 + \text{smaller terms})$$

where α^2 is the fraction of time the unpaired electron is on the copper atom, p is 0.036 cm^{-1} and K_0 is about 0.43. The α^2 values for the above complexes in the given solvents indicate that the bonding is quite covalent in nature and is delocalised over the copper and ligand orbitals. The α^2 values are higher in pyridine than in dimethylformamide and dioxane (Table 1) which is a result of the donation of charge by the solvent molecules along with the Z -axis to the central copper ion. The donation of electrons to the copper from the axial ligand causes a back-donation to the inplane-ligands, which results in an increase in α^2 values in pyridine.

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Synthesis, Characterisation and Electrical Properties of Coordination Polymers of Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Polyhydroxyquinones

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THE dihydroxyquinones are capable of being tetra-functional and form linear polymers when allowed to react with suitable metal ions. Singh *et al.*¹ reported the synthesis and characterisation of a few metal chelate polymers with 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of coordination polymers of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (DHBQ), 5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (DHNQ), 2,3,5,6-tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (THBQ) and 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (DHAQ). The order of the

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Dielectric const.	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	δ AC Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	δ DC Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹
				C	H	M				
1.	DHBQ(L ₁)	213	Orange yellow	56.20 (51.40)	0.40 (0.38)	—	2.90	9.15	—	7.87 $\times 10^{-12}$
2.	Zn-DHBQ	415	Rose	30.59 (30.09)	2.77 (2.53)	27.29 (27.31)	3.39	36.66	2.45 $\times 10^{-7}$	4.06 $\times 10^{-12}$
3.	Cu-DHBQ	325	Snuff	34.76 (35.74)	0.992 (1.00)	30.80 (31.52)	4.02	15.90	—	7.12 $\times 10^{-11}$
4.	DHNQ(L ₂)	235	Dark bluish violet	63.20 (63.15)	3.22 (3.15)	—	3.43	53.38	2.91 $\times 10^{-6}$	1.15 $\times 10^{-11}$
5.	Cu-DHNQ	412	Violet	48.50 (50.89)	2.27 (1.90)	25.30 (25.25)	4.01	37.85	1.56 $\times 10^{-6}$	3.13 $\times 10^{-10}$
6.	Zn-DHNQ	358	Blue	41.02 (41.48)	3.06 (2.76)	22.60 (22.59)	19.26	27.45	6.21 $\times 10^{-5}$	1.60 $\times 10^{-10}$
7.	THBQ(L ₃)	300	Violet	42.01 (41.86)	2.41 (2.38)	—	3.76	9.37	—	3.37 $\times 10^{-10}$
8.	Cu-THBQ	350	Brown	19.42 (21.78)	0.82 (1.00)	38.40 (38.38)	12.95	8.00	1.36 $\times 10^{-5}$	5.11 $\times 10^{-9}$
9.	Zn-THBQ	280	Maroon	17.69 (17.71)	2.91 (2.97)	31.40 (32.10)	10.98	16.46	5.49 $\times 10^{-6}$	2.12 $\times 10^{-9}$
10.	DHAQ(L ₄)	410	Orange	69.80 (70.00)	3.88 (3.33)	—	2.29	18.23	5.06 $\times 10^{-8}$	7.23 $\times 10^{-11}$
11.	Zn-DHAQ	480	Dark	54.89 (55.37)	2.00 (1.97)	19.34 (19.26)	4.07	39.04	2.26 $\times 10^{-7}$	5.29 $\times 10^{-12}$

reaction and activation energies have been calculated for the different polymer from D.S.C. The electrical properties like dielectric constant and conductivities have been measured.

Experimental

DHBQ and DHNQ were prepared and purified by reported methods^{2,3}. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc and from their m.ps. THBQ and DHAQ were purchased from Aldrich.

The metal chelate polymers were synthesised by mixing equimolar alcoholic solutions of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} acetates and the ligands. The pH of the solutions was adjusted to 7–8 using sodium acetate. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h on a water-bath and the separated solids were washed with hot water and ethanol, dried under reduced pressure for about 48 h and then kept over P₂O₅.

The elemental analysis of the metal chelate polymers were obtained from microanalytical laboratory, Calcutta. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer in nujol using CsI windows and the reflectance spectra on a Shimadzu MPS-5000 spectrophotometer and the esr spectra on a Varian E-4 instrument. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by using Gouy balance. X-Ray diffraction was obtained with the help of a Philips powder diffractometer using CuK α radiation. The D.S.C. was recorded on a Mettler TA 2000C instrument. The dielectric constant (ϵ) (1–100 KHz) and loss ($\tan \delta$) were measured at room temperature using A GR 1620 A capacitance assembly in conjunction with a laboratory built three-terminal cell. An Agronic 72 external oscillator was used at high frequencies. For dielectric measurements, the samples (1–3 mm \times 1 cm dia) were dried in vacuum desiccator

over P₂O₅ before taking measurements. The conductivity (σ) was evaluated using the relation, $\sigma = E\epsilon_0 \omega \tan \delta$, where ϵ_0 is the vacuum dielectric constant and ω the angular frequency. D.C. conductivity at room temperature was measured using a Keithley 610C electrometer.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are dark coloured, and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. However, they are sparingly soluble in DMSO and DMF.

Elemental analyses of the compounds (Table I) indicate that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 1.

Infrared spectrum of the ligand exhibits a band in the region 3 300–3 120 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic). The sharp ligand band at 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=O of the ketonic group) shifts to lower frequency (Δ 20 cm⁻¹) in the complexes suggesting coordination of the ligand via carbonyl oxygen. A strong phenolic C–O absorption at 1 130 cm⁻¹ in the ligand shifts to lower energy suggesting coordination of oxygen of the phenolic group⁴. In all the complexes a broad band is observed at 3 400–3 050 cm⁻¹ attributed to the coordinated water molecule⁵. A strong ligand band at 1 310 cm⁻¹ may be due to in-plane bending OH (phenolic) vibration. All polychelates show this band and thus confirming the presence of chelated water⁶. The presence of M–O bond is supported by a band at 350–500 cm⁻¹.

The reflectance spectra of the ligands exhibit bands around (382 nm) corresponding to $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transition. The shift in the band in the Zn^{II} polymers indicates the participation of lone-pair of electrons in chelation. The reflectance spectra of the Cu^{II} polymer indicate two absorption bands (Table I).

The first band around 590 nm corresponds to ${}^2T_{2-g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ of distorted octahedral geometry and the other band around 378 nm corresponds to charge transfer band⁷.

The spectra of the compounds after exposure to the uv radiation show that there is no effect of radiation on the geometry the compounds.

Magnetic moment data of the polymers indicate that the Cu^{II} polymers are paramagnetic whereas the Zn^{II} polymers diamagnetic. The magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} polymers with DHBQ, DHNQ and THBQ are found to be 1.82, 1.90 and 1.84 respectively, and are consistent with the presence of a single unpaired electron.

The number of X-ray reflections obtained for the parent compounds (ligands) are more than that obtained for the polymers of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II}. The reduction in the number of X-ray reflections in the final compounds reveals that the degree of crystallinity is reduced in the polymeric compounds of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} showing the amorphous trend. From esr spectra, the $g_{||}$ values are found to be 2.305 and 2.347 and g_{\perp} values 2.086 and 2.239 respectively for Cu-DHBQ and Cu-DHNQ. The G values are found to be 2.159 and 2.270 respectively for the above Cu^{II} complexes. The values obtained for all the compounds are greater than 2.3 which indicates that the bonds between metal and oxygen are ionic and the bond strength in polychelates of dihydroxynaphthaquinone is more ionic than that of dihydroxybenzoquinone⁸. From D.S.C. plots (Fig. 1), endothermicity, decomposition temperatures and activation energies have been evaluated (Table 2).

Fig. 1. D.S.C. plots of complexes.

The data indicate that these polymers decompose in a gradual manner when compared to the ligands. It was observed that the thermal stabilities of the polymers are high. Orders of thermal decomposition and the corresponding activation energies have been evaluated⁹ (Table 2) and the order of reaction in each case is inferred to be of first order. The presence of alternate single and double bond system in polychelates provides a suitable channel for the flow of electrons and exhibits unusual electrical properties¹⁰.

Keeping this in view, D.C. and A.C. conductivities and relative dielectric constants of DHBQ, DHNQ, THBQ and DHAQ and their polymers with Zn^{II} have been studied.

The plot of dielectric constant vs frequency (Fig. 2) shows that dielectric constant for dihydroxybenzoquinone is frequency-independent throughout the range of measurement and the value is 2.9. For

Fig. 2. Plots of dielectric constant vs frequency of complexes.

dihydroxynaphthoquinone and tetrahydroxybenzoquinone, the dielectric constant is also frequency-independent with a slight increase at lower frequencies. The values at 100 KHz for the ligands and the corresponding polymers are shown in Table 1. The dielectric constants of the polymers are higher than that of the ligands.

For dihydroxybenzoquinone the dielectric loss (Fig. 3) is negligible throughout the range of frequencies whereas for dihydroxynaphthoquinone and tetrahydroxybenzoquinone frequency dependent loss is observed. For tetrahydroxybenzoquinone loss is negligible beyond 50 KHz, below which an

